

Invitation to Participate in Research

STUDY: "Anonymous Name", carried out by the Anonymous Institution.

I, _____, authorize my child, _____ to participate in the study mentioned above.

This study is free of charge, and your child's name and activities will be kept confidential. Your child will do the usual math activities in the classroom, and we will use these tasks to develop an application to facilitate teachers' work and contribute to education. We reinforce the importance of your contribution to this research project and thank you in advance for considering collaborating with our research.

The data collected will be stored under Anonymous's responsibility and under Anonymous's custody.

If you have any doubts about the ethical aspects of this study, you can consult:

Responsible for the study: Anonymous

Email: Anonymous

Signature of the responsible